
Western Ukrainian Choreographers – Representatives Of Today's Modern Dance

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Abstract. *The aim of the research is to study in detail the work of Ukrainian choreographers - representatives of the "modern" style of Western Ukraine in particular. The research methodology consists in the application of several approaches: analytical for the study of literature on the topic of the article and system; using a range of methods: biographical, culturological, comparative-historical, theoretical generalization - comprehensively achieving the stated goal. Due to the biographical method, we considered the professional and creative experience of choreographers, which explains the sources of their work. The comparative-historical method helped us to study the historically formed features of modern dance, to note its structural, due to which we determined the differences between the previous experience of choreographers and modern choreographic research. The scientific novelty of the study is that we are the first to trace the features of modern dance style in the productions of famous choreographers of Ukraine I.V. Mazur, O.B.Lan, O.V. Martyniuk, A.S. Safonov, S.V. Naenko. The research of this issue helped to understand the main trends in the development of contemporary choreographic art in Ukraine, which are to create a national school of modern dance and the use of choreographic vocabulary in ethnic productions. Conclusions: Due to the research, we followed the development of modern dance on the example of the work of Western Ukrainian choreographers listed above. Our research proves that Ukrainian choreography does not deviate from modern fashion trends. The choreographers of our country develop a fashionable pro-European culture of modern dance in their work, create ballet performances in this style and continue to experiment in their own search for lexical material. Art analysis of the leading Western Ukrainian choreographers of modern dance allowed us to identify special cultural features of modern dance in Western Ukraine, which is manifested in the combination of modern dance with national traditions and the creation of an academic school of this style under the influence of national culture.*

Key words: *modern dance, balletmaster, choreographer, ballet performances, art analysis.*

I. Introduction

Contemporary choreography in Ukraine is the issue that has been already considered in the scientific sources. However, the work of balletmasters and choreographers working in the modern style is still superficially considered, so their work should be studied and analyzed in detail in order to understand the sources and foundations that are included in modern Ukrainian dance. Analysis of the work of choreographers of modern-

dance in Ukraine allows to solve this problem, to find the key features of modern dance inherent in Ukrainian choreographers and to find the original sources of their work.

Numerous works of Ukrainian art critics, such as V.V. Pastukh (1999) [1], M.M. Pogrebnyak (2009; 2021) [3,4], N.O. Chilikina (2014) [6], D.I. Sharikov (2010) [7], and others. In particular, M.M. Pogrebnyak provides a picture of the functioning of modern-dance in the choreographic culture of the twentieth century. She identified aesthetic features and scientifically formulates criteria for classifying choreographic works in the style of "modern"; defines the concept of modern dance school [4, p.57]. In her doctoral research, the first time modern-dance is presented as a differentiated phenomenon and scientifically formulated criteria for classifying choreographic works as its varieties, as well as other stylistic trends in theatrical dance in ballet XX – beginning XXI century. In the fourth chapter of the monograph, the researcher specifies the names of some Ukrainian choreographers-representatives of the dance "modern" XX-beginning XXI century. (B. Nizhynska, G. Mayorov, M. Arnaudova, G. Kovtun, A. Rubina, O. Nikolaev, etc.); discovers ways to master the aesthetics of "modern" style in Ukrainian ballet of the XX - early XXI century. [3, p.55].

But the more detailed research of the works of Ukrainian choreographers of the "modern" style today in Western Ukraine, in particular, remains outside the existing scientific research. Accordingly, *the aim* of the work is a detailed studying of the works of Ukrainian choreographers - representatives of the "modern" style of Western Ukraine.

Presenting of the main material. Modern-dance is one of the stylistic trends of modern theatrical dance, which emerged in the early twentieth century in the United States and Europe. According to the research of Pogrebnyak M.M. [4, p.42] definition of the term modern dance as a special aesthetic-philosophical and artistic-aesthetic practice was carried out in accordance with a certain set of "philosophical", aesthetic and technical principles, namely:

The "philosophical" principle is the main formative factor of modern dance and is the desire to directly know the essence of things, phenomena, personalities, discovering their "face" by means of unconditional movement in accordance with the worldview of the artist.

Aesthetic principles: rejection of the conventions of historical and everyday, complete freedom of form.

Technical principles: collapse, isolation, polyrhythm, polycentry, impulse, relaxation, tension [4, p. 54-55].

Based on the meaning of this term, we have made an attempt to specify the names of the Western Ukrainian choreographers - representatives of this style of dance of today, namely I.V. Mazur, O.B. Lan, O.V.Martyniuk, A.S. Safonov, S.V. Naenko.

The most individual techniques of modern dance are characterized by the rejection of the classical inversion and rounded positions of the hands, the need to keep the "aplomb" or as much as possible to straighten your feet. In addition, most modern-dance techniques can be performed barefoot instead of classical pointe shoes and ballet shoes.

Of course, the choreographers try to bring this style closer to free plasticity, so that movements become free from restrictions in bodily forms [3, p.56].

There are various modern dance techniques, most of which are based on the abandonment of classical canons and the search for new choreographic vocabulary.

Modern choreographers of Ukraine are increasingly turning to the vocabulary of modern dance, seeking to show the inner world of the heroes through body art. Modern choreography is used in productions of drama theaters, opera and ballet theaters, modern dance groups, amateur and professional, modern art dance is used in circus productions and dance shows. Of course, to say that this direction currently occupies a leading position in the work of choreographers, it would be an exaggeration, because one style is replaced by another: jazz dance, modern jazz, folk-modern, contemporary and others. The audience perceives performances in this style differently, first of all the audience try to understand it without delving into details, superficially, without immersing themselves in the inner world of the creator, his experiences and feelings. After all, this was a prerequisite for the emergence of modern-style, and then the dance direction [3, 57]. It is difficult to judge how

deeply this choreographer of Ukraine is aware of this aspect, because for this purpose it is necessary to study in detail their work and the path they have taken, and where exactly they found inspiration for their choreography.

Art critic Plakhotnyuk O.A. examining the philosophical perception of dance in the context of the development of contemporary art, notes: the existing versatile direction of modern choreographic art. Here the philosophical basis is a certain source of choreographic contact of independent modern-dance cultures, creators, authors, for example, when one participant discovers and studies the dance of another, introduces its basic principles to his creative work through their individual properties of dance perception, characteristics and properties the physical apparatus of the dancer, his body on the one hand and views on the other, thus sometimes there is a completely new philosophical interpretation of modern-dance "[2, p. 44].

It is worth mentioning the representatives of modern-dance in Ukraine, who were the first in our country to turn to this style: Alla Rubina, Rada Poklitaru, Lyudmila Popovych and Tatiana Ostroverkh.

Among the young choreographers working in this direction in Ukraine, we should mention Khrystyna Shyshkareva, Tetyana Vynokurova, Anton Ovchinnikov and others. These are representatives of the modern generation of modern-dance choreographers of Ukraine. They work and inspire other choreographers of our country to involve this style in modern productions. However, our research concerns the work of choreographers from Western Ukraine, who are currently working in this direction. Among them are such choreographers as O.B. Lan, O.V. Martyniuk, I.V. Mazur, A.S. Safonov, O.A. Plakhotnyuk, S.V. Naenko and others.

The choreography of Lviv region developed under the influence of Western European culture and artistic exchange with the leading choreographers of the capital of Ukraine Kyiv Ala Rubina, Rada Poklitaru and Khrystyna Shyshkareva. However, the work of Western Ukrainian choreographers is saturated with bright national colors, as well as technical means of modern-dance [1, p.72].

Iryna Volodymyrivna Mazur should be named a well-known choreographer of modern-dance in the Lviv region. She is a student of the famous choreographer of Lviv of the XX century *Vikentiy Rudchuk*. In 1986, after five years of working as a dancer in the jazz ballet of *Manuela Schwartz* in Germany, Irina and her husband, director Stefan Mazur, created the ballet "Life" in Lviv.

Together with the People's Artist of Ukraine Ruslana Lyzhychko, they won the first victory of Ukraine at the Eurovision Song Contest in 2004, and also represented Ukraine with both solo programs and Ruslana's program "Wild Dances" in more than 50 countries in 2004-2006.

In 2005, during the Eurovision Song Contest in Kyiv, the ballet presented a choreographic suite "Memories of Fire". The longest tour (30 concerts in 20 days) of the ballet took place in the United Kingdom. The most massive was his performance in Seoul at the Chamshil Olympic Stadium in the presence of one hundred thousands spectators (September 2009). Thanks to the creative experience gained during almost 30 years of active concert activity, the ballet "Life" has become a unique choreographic "laboratory": a synthesis of ethno-authenticity, Eastern European modernism and jazz, and works in the direction of Street dance allows to display stories in the style of «Dance Action». Each composition is not only a dance with elements of drama, it is a theatrical-dance miniature [8].

Another well-known choreographer of the Lviv region in the field of modern dance is the head of the modern ballet "Aquerias" *Oksana Borysivna Lan*. She is a well-known Ukrainian choreographer and teacher, a member of the National Union of Choreographers of Ukraine, Honored Artist of Ukraine (2011).

O.B. Lan has graduated the Lviv Polygraphic Institute in 1982. In 1991 she has graduated the Kyiv Institute of Culture (teachers - *Anelia Obertynska*, *Volodymyr Tolubko*, etc.). She has lived in Lviv since 1979. From 1979 to 1981 she worked as a soloist of the first in Ukraine group of modern choreography "Rock Ballet" of the Palace of Youth "Romantic". During 1983-1984 she was the leader of the modern-dance ensemble "Fantasy". From 1985 to 1991 he was the founder and leader of the folk dance ensemble "Festival" of the House of Culture of the Lviv Bus Plant. Since 1991 she has been the founder and director of the modern ballet «Aquerias», for which she has created more than 60 compositions. Since 1995, she has been the first in Ukraine to combine jazz-modern dance with elements of Ukrainian folklore in the dance composition "Galician Suite - Lviv Florists". Since 1996 he has been collaborating with the People's Artist of Ukraine Sofia Rotaru as a choreographer.

Professional dancer and teacher *Olena Vyacheslavivna Martyniuk*, an honored figure of pop art of Ukraine, who works in this direction, is also engaged in the development of modern style in Lviv. O.V. Martyniuk has been working for a long time in the modern ballet "Aquerias" by Oksana Lan - the People's Ensemble of Ukraine, and is also the head of the art studio "About Dance". In 2018, O.V. Martyniuk organized her own studio of modern-dance fans "Dance Body & Mind". O.V. Martyniuk is the author of articles on the development of modern choreography, as well as the manual "Methods of teaching modern dance", which is ready for publication.

Anton Sergeevich Safonov - dancer, choreographer, engaged in research, development and teaching of contemporary dance in Ukraine. As an artist he is developing in the direction of modern choreography. He works in the style of mostly contemporary dance, although he began his own search in contemporary choreography, including the style of modern-dance. A.S. Safonov is a free artist who does not stop in his own development and self-improvement.

From his personal creative experience he is the founder and choreographer of «The third person» dance theater in Kherson, a participant of «Zelyonka Fest»; co-authored with Anton Ovchinnikov a dance performance "Fly in da Milk", who are creator of Black O! Range Dance Theater.

Anton Safonov researches dance physical practices, heals people, helps to find internal resources by squeezing the methods of martial arts, dance, yoga and other areas of work with the body and mind. He is the curator of the dance projects «Point of creation», the project "Children of Change".

In addition to the development of amateur art of modern dance, it is worth focusing on professional ballet and drama performances, which use this direction. For example, in the Lviv National Opera and Ballet Theater. Solomiya Krushelnytska staged ballet performances in the modern style, namely "Closer Than Love" by A. Shoshin, "Pulcinella", "Sacred Spring" by Marcello Alferi, the famous Italian balletmaster.

Radu Poclitaru at the National Opera and Ballet Theater named after T.G. Shevchenko staged ballets "The Master and Margarita", "Dante", "Pictures from the exhibition", his interpretation of "Sacred Spring" by Ihor Stravinsky [4, p. 78].

In Lviv, the soloist of the Lviv National Opera and Ballet Theater named after Solomiya Krushelnytska *Hanna Sapunkova* together with choreographer *Serhiy Viktorovych Naenko* in 2018 staged choreography for the performances "Bolero", "Carmen Suite", "Salomeya" by Oscar Wilde at the Lesya Kurbas Lviv Drama Theater. Also it was choreographed in the modern style for the dramatic play "Portrait of Dorian Gray" in the same theater in 2021, directed by Boris Ozerov, choreographed by Victor Prokopenko. The play combines classic modernism with demi classics.

These performances are a well-deserved success with the audience, although the first attempts to instill modern choreography for the Ukrainian audience were quite unsuccessful. They encourage the audience to think, empathize, look for answers to questions asked by the director.

The scientific novelty of the study is that we are the first to trace the features of modern dance style in the productions of famous choreographers of Ukraine I.V. Mazur, O.B.Lan, O.V. Martyniuk, A.S. Safonov, S.V. Naenko. The research of this issue helped to understand the main trends in the development of contemporary choreographic art in Ukraine, which are to create a national school of modern-dance and the use of choreographic vocabulary in ethnic productions.

II. Conclusions

Due to the research, we followed the development of modern-dance on the example of the work of Western Ukrainian choreographers listed above. Our research proves that Ukrainian choreography does not deviate from modern fashion trends. The choreographers of our country develop a pro-European culture of modern dance in their work, create ballet performances in this style and continue to experiment in their own search for lexical material. Art analysis of the leading Western Ukrainian choreographers of modern-dance allowed us to identify special cultural features of modern-dance in Western Ukraine, which is manifested in the combination of modern -dance with national traditions and the creation of an academic school of this style under the influence of national culture.

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